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Organisational Climate and Employees Productivity Among Non-Academic Staff in Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma, Edo State, South-South, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between organizational climate and employees' productivity in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, South-South, Nigeria. The study adopted the correlational research design. The area of the study is Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma, Edo State. The institution is located along express Way, KM 70 Benin Auchu Road, Benin City. The population of the study was made up of all the 1,432 non-teaching staff in all the units which the non-teaching staff function in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. The purposive sampling technique was adopted in selecting 8 units/department of the non-teaching staff while the simple random sampling technique was adopted in selecting a sample size of 300 non teaching staff from units/department in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. These included Verification unit, Audit, Bursary, Post-Graduate Studies, Admission Unit, Information Communication Technology (ICT) Unit, Exams and Records and Senate Services Unit. Both primary and secondary data were the main sources of data used in this study. The study used panel secondary data to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses. The secondary data were obtained using questionnaire. An adapted questionnaire titled "Organizational Climate and Employees Productivity Questionnaire" (OCEPQ) was used to elicit responses from the respondents. The method which was adopted in the analysis of data for this study is the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) statistical tool using SPSS version 20. The study revealed that there is a significant relationship between job autonomy, job involvement, concern for employee welfare, organizational facilities and employees' productivity in Ambrose Alli university, Ekpoma, Edo State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that the university management should ensure that employees are given a reasonable and commendable job autonomy in their various unit as this would enhance their level of job productivity.

Keywords: Organisational Climate, Productivity, Autonomy, Involvement, Welfare, facilities

Introduction

Over the years, there has been increasing focus on the relationship between management and employees both in the business and in academic world since 1930s. Attitudes of the employees towards their organization, owing to their work environment, are important issues in organizational behavior literature. Employee behavior in

organizations due to their personal characteristics as well as the environment in which they work. In this regard, organizational climate is an important aspect in order to understand employee's work-related behavior.

Employees' job attitudes are affected by a wide range of organizational characteristics and social relationships, which the employees' work environment. When referring to employees' perceptions of their working environments, it is possible to find a variety of terms and definitions such as organizational climate, psychological climate, collective climate, and organizational culture. It appears that organizational climate is one of the most important issues regarding organizational environment, which has a direct relationship with employee behavior. Since late 1960s, organizational climate has been a popular topic discussed in organizational behavior literature and is considered as a significant viewpoint in order to comprehend employee's work-related attitudes and behaviors.

It is believed that the work environment is perceived by employees as favourable when benefits, resources and workload are reasonable and fair, equitable and mutual respect between employers and employees which culminates in steady, beneficial work outcomes and attitude. It is clear that creating a healthy, inspiring organisational climate is imperative to maximizing the potentials of employees. A clear understanding of variables of climate assists management to channel struggles towards the attainment of organisational goals. The needs and concerns of people about work procedures and processes are provided via meaningful attention to variables that makeup organisational climate. In other words, managers must understand many and interrelated work procedures that arouse staff needs and ways they can be inspired for better performance on the job.

Organisational climate can be seen as an illustrative idea that mirrors the regular view and understanding of all individuals with respect to the different segment of the organisation, for example, structure, frameworks and practices (McMurray, 2003). This organisational climate fundamentally alludes to the experience of employees in the organisation. Organisational climate centers on discernment. Brown and Brooks (2002).

Alomian (2010) viewed organisational climate as a description of the internal work environment with all its dimensions and physical and social elements. Apparently, the physical and social elements include the nature of power, leadership styles, organisational design or structure, communication, values and behavioral norms. However, Alajmi (2016) see a of organisational climate as a set of characteristics that distinguish and describe one organisation from another. The set of distinctive characteristics emanates from internal and external factors of the organisation that exert positive or negative influence on the behaviour of employees in the work environment. From his point of view, organisational climate is not in isolation from the surrounding environment of the organisation as the organisation derives many of its inputs from its environment.

It is important to note that as much as organisational climate is not void of its environment, it is bound to be influenced by environmental factors. Thus, creating a work friendly atmosphere for employee performance is very essential to overall organisational outcomes since job performance is under individual's control and it is affected by some certain factors such as management style, pay status, working environment, facilities, climate factors, growth potentials in the job (Campbell, 1990). Organisations nowadays are facing more challenges than ever before (Nair 2016). As no organisation exists independent of its immediate environment, organisational climate is constantly affected by factors prevalent in the environment irrespective of the formation or composition of any organisation. It demands that organisation constantly seek to improve performance in order to remain relevant among its competitors.

In the same vein, Nurharani, Ivughminah (2013) emphasized on the importance of organisational climate in influencing positive outcomes as individuals who perceive work procedures and processes to be friendly and favourable will stay and continue to put in their best towards the achievement of organisational objectives and goals. Most of these factors when properly harnessed and applied will climax job productivity of to employees. It is in this light that in recent times, measures of enhancing employee's performance is viewed as an issue of top priority to every management team. Creating a supportive work environment has become a competitive management technique as a good working climate influences staff motivation, drive and self-confidence on the job performance. Understanding organisational climate becomes an important factor to be considered. Therefore

an evaluation of organisational climate vis-a-vis employee job productivity will help to determine employee productivity and consequently organisational effectiveness.

Organisations that can create environments that employees see as nonmalignant and in which they can accomplish their maximum capacity are research as a key source of competitive advantage (Brown & Leigh, 1996). Organisational climate can accordingly be viewed as a major variable in effective organisations. In the light of this, the variables which are believed to determine the organizational climate of an organization are job autonomy, employee involvement, concern for employee welfare and organizational facilities.

job autonomy is conceptualized as the degree of power that employees have to delegate their own task and other job activities, which specifically concerns on the voluntary power and freedom towards the work goals, task elements arrangement and determining the process and the pace of task that are conducted. Job autonomy is the extent to which the job offers real freedom, independence, and discretion to the individual in scheduling the work and to determine the procedures to be used and carried out (Dysvik and Kuvaas 2011; Humphrey, Nahrgang, & Morgeson, 2007). It is also specifically refers to self rule and independence of an employees in terms of decision making. In the light of the foregoing, it is to be noted that job autonomy is also commonly associated with choice and freedom of employees that exist in the job to perform variety of task which enriches the job domain and develop employees competency in terms of creativity and problem resolution as it gives employee the authority and enable them to find out solutions personally (Wang & Netemyer, 2002).

Employee job involvement is another aspect of organisation climate which is believed to enhance the job productivity of employees in an organization. Job involvement refers to a state of psychological identification with work or the degree to which a job is central to a person's. From an organizational perspective, job involvement is regarded as the key to unlocking employee motivation and increasing productivity and from an individual perspectives, job involvement constitutes a key to motivation, performance, personal growth, and satisfaction in the workplace. Job involvement contributes importantly to organizational effectiveness, productivity, and morale by engaging employees deeply in their work and making it a meaningful and fulfilling experience Wainaina, Iravo and Waitit (2014). It is however believed that Job involvement enhances work performance of employees by motivating them to exert greater effort and use their creativity to solve problems and work intelligently.

The concern for employee welfare is another organizational climate variable which is believed to affects the job productivity of employees. Employee welfare means anything done for the comfort and (intellectual or social) improvement of the employees, over and above the wages paid. In simple words, it means "the efforts to make life worth living for workmen." It includes various services, facilities and amenities provided to employees for their betterment. These facilities may be provided voluntarily by the organisation, or statutory provisions may compel them to provide these amenities; or these may be undertaken by the government or trade unions, if they have the required funds. The objectives of employee welfare are to improve the life of the working class, to bring about holistic development of the personality of the worker etc. Employee welfare is in the interest of employee, employer and the society in gernal. It allows workers to perform their work in healthy and favorable environment. Thus enhances, it improves efficiency of workers and keeps them content, thereby contributing to high employee morale. It also develops a sense of responsibility and dignity amongst the workers and thus makes them good citizens of the nation.

Organizational facilities is another aspect of organizational climate which could have a relationship with employees productivity. Organizational facilities are made up of the land and all the physical structure on it. It refers to the organizational buildings, the play grounds, the equipment and other material resources provided in the organization that can motivate workers for higher productivity . It is believed that the site, building, furniture and pieces of equipment's available in the organization contribute positively to employees productivity. It is to be noted that the organizational facilities available within an organization have positive relationship with employees comfort and level of job productivity which in turn leads to the attainment of goals set.

On the other hand, employee productivity is defined as the amount of work (or output) produced by an employee in a specific period of time. As a manager, it's important to understand how long it takes your teammates to complete specific tasks.

Statement of the Problem

The productivity of employees in most tertiary institution in Nigeria University including Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria seems to be on the decrease and this has created worries among stakeholders of the Nigerian educational sector and well as these in police, business world, religious body and the like. The low level of job productivity is evident in the performance of assigned duties by both academic and non-academic staff of the institution, especially in the area of punctuality and regularity to school. Many non-teaching staff of the institution are have also been observed not to be taking active role in the effective discharge of their duties. Other observations include absenteeism from duties posts, poor attitude towards their duties, insecurity in the discharge of their duties, attendances at meetings, poor evaluation, among others. Many researchers like Ofeimu and Kolawole (2017), Igbogi (2018) and Gikunda (2016) have all noted that employees of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma are not performing their duties the way they ought to and this tends to affect the total output of the institution.

This poor productivity of employees has created worry and questions are being asked if the organizational climate is responsible. Employees particularly the non teaching staff of the institution are unwilling to perform their duties effectively; some of them are seen outside the organizational premises and around the organization at the neglect of their responsibility because of inadequate motivation arising from lack of job autonomy, little or no psychological identification with job and inadequate concern for staff welfare. Also, the organizational environment where the employees perform their duties has been in a worrisome state of neglect. To insufficient lighting, and general state of disrepair of school infrastructure and facilities. In the light of this, this study investigates the relationship between organizational climate and employee productivity among non – academic staff of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State Nigeria in focus.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine organizational climate and employee productivity: among non academic staff of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State South-South Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are:

- i. To find out if there is a significant relationship between job autonomy and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State
- ii. To find out if there is a significant relationship between job involvement and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State
- iii. To find out if there is a significant relationship between concern for employee welfare and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State
- iv. To find out if there is significant relationship between organizational facilities and productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli university, Ekpoma, Edo State

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. Is there any significant relationship between job autonomy and productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State?
- ii. Is there any significant relationship between job involvement and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State?
- iii. Is there any significant relationship between concern for employee welfare and productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State?
- iv. Is there any significant relationship between organizational facilities and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- Ho₁ There is no significant relationship between job autonomy and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State
- Ho₂ There is no significant relationship between job involvement and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State
- Ho₃ There is no significant relationship between concern for employee welfare and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State
- Ho₄ There is no significant relationship between organizational facilities and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli university, Ekpoma, Edo State

Concept of Organizational Climate

Organisational climate can be viewed as an illustrative idea that mirrors the regular view and understanding of all individuals with respect to the different components of the organisation, for example, structure, frameworks and practices (McMurray, 2003). Thus, organisational climate essentially and basically alludes to the experience of employees in the organisation. The idea of organisational climate centers on discernment. Brown and Brooks (2002) see climate as the “feeling in the air” and the “atmosphere that employees perceive is created in their organisations due to practices, procedures and rewards.” Based on these clauses, clearly the individual view of employees in the organisation affects the climate. Despite the fact that people contrast in the method they perceive, analyze and interpret information, the climate introduce in the organisation is an aggregate view or recognition (Dormeyer, 2003) as climate is the perceptual or psychological description (Al-Shammari, 1992) of the individual.

Two concepts exist in the organisational climate which is perceptual and descriptive. McMurray (2003) claimed that the opinions and agreement of employees on different organisation elements such as system, structure and practices show the descriptive concept in it. While, climate is defined as the “feeling in the air” and the “atmosphere that employees perceive is formed in their organisations based on procedures, practices and rewards” in the study of Brown and Brooks (2002) and this shows the perceptions concept in organisational climate which affected by the individual perceptions. The organisational climate can be seen as the collective perception of employees even though It is subject to change anytime (Dormeyer, 2003, Al-Shammari, 1992).

The climate in an organisation is influenced by occasions and attribute critical to the organisation, which thus apply a strong impact on the members of organization. The organisational climate has the ability to bring out the general psychological atmosphere of an organisation, and subsequently, may influence the behaviour, fulfillment and inspiration of people in the work environment (Lawler, 1992). Organisational climate is the generally persisting characteristic in an organisation which is recognizes it from different organisations: and typifies members collective perceptions about their organisaitons as for such measurements as self-sufficiency, confide in, cohesiveness, innovation, acknowledgment of fairness and support; (b) collaboration among the members; (c) fills in as a reason for interpreting the circumstance; (d) reflects the culture for predominant standards, qualities and attitudes of the organisation; and (e) serves as an impact for molding behavior (Forehard & Gilmer ,1964., Pritchard & Karasick ,1973).

The expression “climate” generally begins from the theorists of organization. For example Douglas McGregor and Kurt Lewin, utilized the term to allude to climate of social and organisational separately. Ahmed (1998). The climate of the organisation depends on its employees’ sentiments and view of the organisation’s practices, methods and reward frameworks. Organisational climate can be characterized in various ways. Definitions of Litwin and Stringer (1968) which is the most broadly accepted characteristic of organisational climate as an arrangement of the work environment quantifiable properties that is perceived by the general population who live and work in a particular situation and is expected to impact their behaviour and performance.

Organizational climate is one of the most critical issues reasoning organizational environment, which has a direct relationship with employee behavior. Since late 1960s, organizational climate has been a popular topic discussed in organizational behavior literature and is considered as a vital viewpoint in order to comprehend employee's work-related attitudes and behaviors. Payne and Pugh (1971) defined organizational climate as the way in which employees perceive their organization and its purposes. Organizational climate is the aggregates of the environment (Churchill and Walker, 1976). According to Mullins (2010), if organizational culture is defined simply as 'how things are done around here', then organizational climate can be defined as 'how it feels to work around here'.

Griffin and Moorhead (2014) see organizational climate as individual perceptions; recurring patterns of behaviour, attitudes and feelings of employees. Additionally, Robbins and Judge (2003) stated that organizational climate can be regarded as an aspect of culture and defined as team spirit but at the organizational level and according to Uhl-Bien, Schermerhorn and Osborn (2014), one of the most vital aspects in an organization to influence how people behave is organizational culture that can be defined as the shared beliefs and values within the organization. In order to understand how an employee perceives organizational climate, it is necessary to consider the employee's perceptions of the employee of the work situation (including the characteristics of the organization they work for) and the nature of his/her relationships with other people in the same environment (Churchill and Walker, 1976).

Organisational climate refers to the shared perceptions of the employee and the meaning they attach to the policies, practices and procedures they experience in their workplace, as well as to the behaviours they observe being rewarded, supported and expected regarding the human resources of the organization Ahmad, Jasimuddin, Kee 2018, Schneider, Eharhart, Maccey, 2013). Posit that organisational climate encompasses organisational structure and processes, interpersonal relationships, employee behaviour, performance expectation and opportunities for growth.

Concept of Employee Productivity

Employee productivity can be defined as the amount of work (or output) produced by an employee in a specific period of time. Productivity is also defined as a measurement of the efficiency of a person completing a task. However, he stress that productivity is more than just getting things done.

Employee productivity is an assessment of the efficiency of a worker or group of workers. In real terms, productivity is a component which directly affects the profits (Gummesson, 1998; Sels De Wine, Delmatte, Maes, Faems, Forrier 2000 et al., 2006).of the company Productivity may be evaluated in terms of the output of an workers in a specific period of time. Indeed, the productivity of a given worker will be assessed relative to an average out for employees doing similar work. It can also be assessed according to the amount of units of a product or service that an employee handles in a defined time frame (Piana, 2001). As the success of an organization depend solely mainly on the productivity of its employees, therefore, employee productivity has become a critical objective for businesses (Cato & Gordon, 2009; Gummesson, 1998; Sharma & Sharma, 2014).

In recent times, many studies have indentified on one or two ways to measure productivity and since many different approaches are taken, it can be challenging if not completely impossible to compare the results (Nollman, 2013). Overall, there is a lack of an effective and standardized way to evaluate productivity. According to Sharma and Sharma (2014), employee productivity is based on the amount of time that an employee is physically present at his/ her job, besides the extent to which he she is "mentally present" or efficiently working during the presence at the job. Ferreira and Du Plessis (2009) showed that productivity can be assessed in terms of the time spent by an employee actively executing the job he or she was employed to do, in order to produce the desired result expected from an employee's job description of an employee.

Sharma and Sharma (2014), opine that higher productivity results in economic growth, higher profitability, and social progress. It is only by increasing productivity, employees can obtain better wages/ salaries, working conditions and larger employment opportunities. Cato and Gordon (2009) also showed that the alignment of the

strategic vision to employee productivity is a major contributor to the success and well being of an organization. This alignment as a result would motivate and inspire employees to be more creative and innovative, and this ultimately can improve their performance effectiveness to accomplish organizational goals and objectives (Morales et al., 2001; Obdulio, 2014). Moreover, higher productivity tends to increase the competitive advantage through reduction in costs and improvement in quality of output.

Job Autonomy and Employees Productivity

An important work characteristic is autonomy at work and it is defined as the extent to which ones job gives freedom to plan work , select different methods to perform task and also to make decisions (Hackman & Oldham, 1976). When autonomy is enhanced, employees are more involve in attaining new skills and are more problems at work (Parker, 1998). Autonomy has been consistently linked to employee satisfaction as a positive factor (Parker & Wall, 1998). Many other research results also pointed out that autonomy is an essential component for professional development (Hart & Rotem, 1995) and is a positive factor for job satisfaction (Finn, 2001).

Job autonomy is considered as major features of work and has been most extensively studied by researchers in job design characteristics Karasek, Brisson, Kawakami, Houtman, Bongers & Amick, (1998) relate job autonomy with workers' possibilities of making decisions regarding their work. It is conceptualized as the extent of power that employees have to delegate their own task and other job activities, which specifically concerns on the voluntary power and freedom towards the work goals, task elements arrangement and determining the process and the pace of task that are conducted (Kwakman, 2003; Xanthopoulou, Demerouti, Bakker, & Schaufeli, 2007). Based on the numerous research on job autonomy, scholars have generally defined it as the degree to which the job provides substantial freedom, independence, and discretion to the individual in scheduling the work and to determine the procedures to be used and carried out (Hackman & Oldham 1975; Dysvik and Kuvaas 2011; Humphrey, Nahrgang, & Morgeson, 2007).

Several factors that could impact job satisfaction of employees including work autonomy. Castillo and Cano (2004) found that work autonomy was the most motivating aspect for universities faculty member job satisfaction and also highlighted that 'work itself' was the characteristic most satisfying, and 'working conditions' being the least satisfying characteristic of their jobs. Studies such as Parker and Wall (1998) state that employee satisfaction is consistently linked with job autonomy. In area of professional development, research (Manley, 1995) also has indicated that work autonomy could be considered as an essential element. In indicating the importance of work autonomy, Yunki (1999) emphasizes that such autonomy is the most important predicator of employee job satisfaction.

Flexibility has been identified as key elements in entering and staying as an academic (Bellamy, Morey, Watty 2003). Malik (2009) asserted that the work itself and advancement were highly correlated with faculty job satisfaction. Intrinsic factors such as responsibility and the satisfaction with work itself arise from the human ability to personally advance and grow (Malik, 2011). Robbins, Odendall & Roodt (2003) in their study highlight that when a job provides an opportunity for individuals with tasks that stimulate, growth opportunities for personal growth and learning, and the opportunity to be accountable for results, such provides a basis for enhanced job satisfaction. Further, Robbins (2005) opines that jobs that provide chances for using skills and abilities, diversity of tasks, independence and feedback of their performance tend to be preferred by the employees. Meyerape et al (2006) when employees are moderately satisfied with the freedom to choose their own method of work, their level of responsibility, and the amount of variety in their job, the productivity will definitely increased.

Hall, Villeme, Phillippy (1989) opine that the most imperative factor of teacher's motivation is autonomy. They added that teachers are more confident and self initiate when they have autonomy to manage class, design their course, plans how to evaluate in comparison to those teacher who are given instructions for every task to be done.

Parver, Baldwin (2008) they asserted that teacher's empowerment means they have academic freedom i.e they have freedom to plan the lesson, make syllabus, select text books to recommend their students by their own and not by the department ort. Moreover, He elaborated that empowerment of teachers is a process in which teachers extend their capabilities to grow and to solve their problems. The six dimensions of teacher empowerment which are decision making, status, professional growth, autonomy and self efficacy increase their productivity at work.

Rasheed, Aslam & Sarwar (2010) conducted a research to identify the issues of motivation for teachers in higher education of Pakistan.. The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan was taken as case study, the source of the primary data was in depth interviews and questionnaires. The findings of the study have shown that along with compensation and benefits there are some other motivating factors like job design, feedback, empowerment, work environment ,decision making ,recognition and participation motivate teachers in higher education. The unstructured nature of complex jobs, which require workers to exercise judgment, decision-making, creativity, and other discretionary behaviors increase employee productivity. Frese and Zapf (1994) noted that those with discretion and control can more effectively tackle problems because they have the freedom to choose strategies to deal with the situation. Employees who perceive higher levels of autonomy within their practice are more satisfied within their jobs (Taylor& Morgan 2008). The employees rarely make effort to change some of the characteristics of their jobs if they feel that they have no opportunity/freedom to craft their jobs.

Job Involvement and Employees Productivity

Job Involvement is the level of identifying an employee with his or her work, actively participating in his or her work, and regards his performance in his or her work to be more critical for his good (Schiemann, 2011). Job Involvement is level of activity of an individual in participating and evaluating his work which is critical for his self-esteem (Robbins and Judge, 2017). Employees with high levels of Job Involvement firmly recognize correctly and pay attention to the type of work they do. According to Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart & Wright (2016), job involvement is the level of identification of a person in the work he does. Someone who has high Job Involvement will value his job as important to their life.

Thus involvement is fundamentally persuaded by the reading of an employee about his personal picture of life. and then by the organizational qualities and job attributes (Moynihan & Pandey, 2007). This implies that job involvement is that organizational attitude which tells that how much an employee psychologically identifies with the employer organization and how much one believes that his work is significant and enlarges his self-respect (Robbins, 1998: Weidmer, 1998).

Job involvement has been divided into two separate approaches. First approach is viewed as an individual difference variable where job involvement is believed to happen when the possession of particular needs, values or personal characteristics affect individuals to become more or less involved in their jobs. The second approach regards job involvement as a reaction to particular work situation distinctiveness (Ekmekci, 2011). Job involvement has been one of the most useful tools used for increasing employee productivity by improving employee involvement and commitment. Job involvement is related to employees perception that how the job takes place in individual life. As much as an individual is positively influenced by his job, the readiness and accomplishment will automatically increase (Ekmekci, 2011). This means that it also creates the meaning of ownership within employees who are involved in decisions concerning their job and its associated activities. This clearly reveals that those organizations that have job involvement culture, have their employees are more committed with organization than those organizations that do not involve their employees (Khan, Jam, Akbar, Khan, Hijazi, 2011).

Since an individual spends a large segment of time at job and the job of person truthfully affects the future of person's life (Ekmekci, Jam Akbar, Khan, Hijazi 2011). Human resource managers and organizational development practitioners should pay attention on the culture, design and environmental factors which foster the job involvement of the employees. It will not only intensify the organizational commitment but job contentment too and will decrease job strain, turnover intention of the employees respectively (Khan et al., 2011). Similarly,

job involvement also has an important role in the complete performance of organization. Workers with high levels of both job involvement and should be the most inspired because they are attracted by both the job and the organization (Ekmekci, 2011).

The point of interest in the term “job involvement” is the final consequences of this phenomenon that can be explained that if the workers put forth greater efforts for the achievement of the personal and organizational objectives, this will lead to more productivity and at the end, ultimately retained the employee ultimately retain with the organization (Kahn, 1990; Kanungo, 2013; Lawler, 1986;). On the contrary, the employees who are having low degree of involvement are more likely to experience low job satisfaction and hitch to leave the organization. Besides this if they remain with the organization they put their efforts towards non productive work or apply their energy in undesirable ties that are not beneficial for the organization and the productivity decreases (Kanungo, 1981).

Concern for Employee Welfare and Employees Productivity

The issue of staff welfare is an important milestone in human resource management in institutions. Tertiary institutions are supposed to channel their effort towards improved employee performance in order to highlight their quality and relevance. Welfare provision is vital in determining the success of any institute because it is one of the bases of motivation of staff. In order for university management and authorities to manage the performance of teachers employees welfare should be seen as drivers of productivity.

In schools, the teacher is mainly responsible for training the child to become a good and ‘active’ world citizen (Chapin, 2003). Teachers determine the quality of education system, of a country particularly the extent to which the products of education meet the requirements of societal development (Linda, 2008; Türkkahraman, 2012). Therefore teachers must perform in ways that enhance positive schooling (UNESCO, 2007). However, for teachers to ensure that they take the lead in improving education, their performance in terms of how they educate learners has to prove commendable (Onwu and Mogari, 2004). The concept of welfare is concerned with the total wellbeing of employees inside and outside the institution. The term employees welfare refers to the provision of a minimal level of well-being and social support to an employees for improved productivity.

According to Jepkemoi (2014), the provision of well-being to employees is a source of earning and satisfaction which is most likely to increase their productivity owing to the fact that they are motivated and happy. Organizations offers welfare facilities to their employees to keep their motivation levels high. When employees are motivated and satisfied their performance increases to improve their productivity. People join organizations in order to meet and satisfy their needs (financial and non-financial) through statutory and non-statutory welfare programmes (Cole 2006). For the provision of welfare package which is the total compensation and remuneration for workers that contain provision for vocation, study leave, sick leave, relocation expenses, paid holiday, staff training, transportations and accommodation benefits among others must be provided in the organization. Welfare packages are therefore seen the stimulus for greater action that serves as incentive in addition to wages and salaries.

Employee welfare is a comprehensive term that included various services, benefits and facilities offered to them by employers. Lack of effective reward systems for compensating the employees work employees efforts negatively reduces the level of employees work morale and these impacts negatively on organization productivity.

Organizational Facilities and Employee Productivity

According to Osuji (2016), appearance and general condition of organizational facilities are the striking basis upon which many parents and friends of any educational institution make the initial judgment about the quality of what goes on in the organization. Fabunmi (2007) in support of this asserted that organizational facilities when provided will aid teaching and learning programme and consequently improve productivity of employees. Organizational facilities are the transport facilities, free launch, secure and safe security facilities, spacious and

air conditional offices etc. possible and easier. Lack of organizational facilities results in depreciation employees whether teaching or non teaching.

Organizational facilities are needed for developing cognitive area of knowledge, abilities and skill, which are prerequisites for academic achievement. They are important for developing values, commitment, positive emotions and social interactional sensitivity in employees. In addition, they help the organizational to develop the hands and muscles of employees.

Mulkeen (2005) is of the opinion that the insufficient lack of resources in a organizational also contributes to employee job ineffectiveness. Mulkeen (2005) noted that a large percentage of new employees in the Ghana said they did not have access to sufficient basic supplies. Most employees had to use their own money to equip their classroom. Of the employees interviewed, 26 percent report spending \$300 to \$1000 of their own funds on classroom supplies over the year, 14 percent spent \$100 to \$200, and 12 percent \$50 to \$75. In addition to this, most employees report that they do not have enough textbooks or that the textbooks they do have are in poor condition.

Theoretical Framework

The study is rested on the Social Exchange Theory based on Blau (1964) cited in Okoli (2008). Social Exchange Theory can be used to explain the relationship between organizational climate and employee productivity. Within the whims and caprices of social exchange theory. The employer (the university management) is committed to building a relationship of long term employment with the employees (non-academic staff) by meeting their needs via offering the non-academic staff conducive workplace climate, opportunities for growth, safe and secured working conditions, administrative support etc. Non-academic staff will be committed in enhancing performance in return. One of the major features of a “Social Exchange Theory” is a consenting to build a long- term relationship between the employer and employees. The consent of the university management (employer) is exhibited by the endeavor of the university management to satisfy the needs of non-academic staff (employees). By offering them with a good workplace climate and better management practice. These satisfied non-academic staff think up a long tenured employment anxious to take additional care of their productive activities for their employing organization and willing to make optimal struggle to contribute to the goals of the organization (Okoli, 2008).

Review of Empirical Studies

Terason (2018) examined the influence of job autonomy on job satisfaction in thai fitness trainer professionals: A moderation analysis. The relationship between job autonomy and job satisfaction was found to depend on whether one was assigned managerial responsibility.

Amarasena, Ajward and Haque (2015) carried out a study on the impact of work autonomy on job satisfaction of academic staff: An empirical examination of government universities in Sri Lanka. Nevertheless, it was found that marital status and number of children had no impact on the perception of work autonomy. In terms of the regression analysis conducted, it was found out that the work autonomy was a highly significant factor affecting the academic staff members’ overall job satisfaction of state. Mwori, Wachira and Mwaura (2021) examined job autonomy and employee performance in the County Government of Isiolo, Kenya. The study concluded that job autonomy influences employee performance in county government of Isiolo.

Kusmaningtyas and Nugroho (2020) carried out a study on the effect of job involvement on employee performance through work engagement at bank Jatim. The study proves that Job Involvement has a significant influence on Work Engagement, but Job Involvement has no significant influence on Employee Performance, while Work Engagement has a significant influence on Employee Performance. Mazayed, Khan, Kundi, Qureshi Akhtar & Bila (2014) carried out a study on assessing the impact of job involvement and commitment on organizational productivity in the Arab/Gulf countries. Findings of the study reveal significant positive relationship between job involvements, employee’s commitment and organizational productivity. The study in

conclusion clearly indicate that organizations with high job involvement and employees' commitment are performing well than organizations with little job involvement and low employees' commitment.

Agusioma, Nyakwara and Mwit (2019) examined the influence of staff welfare on employee performance at public service commission in Kenya. The study found that staff welfare was positively and significantly affected employee performance. Therefore an increase in these factors will result in increased accessibility to increased employee performance. The study concludes that staff welfare is essential in creating a sense of recognition and satisfaction among the employees which improves their productivity. Kiptum (2018) investigated influence of organizational physical environment on employees' satisfaction in selected public primary organizations in Elgeyo Marakwet County, Kenya. The inferential statistics comprised of Pearson product moment and multiple regression. The multiple regression model, shows that physical environment account for 54.4% variation in employees' satisfaction. The physical facilities, classroom arrangement and work environment had significant relationship with employees' satisfaction. The organizational physical facilities, work environment, and classroom arrangement positively influenced employees' satisfaction.

Ibrahim (2009) assessed the Relationship between organizational facility conditions and the delivery of instruction. The findings of the study indicated that six of the ten facility conditions are statically and positively associated with the delivery of instruction. These six facility conditions significantly predicted the delivery of instruction after controlling other extraneous or plausible variables. Facility conditions accounted for 43 percent of the explained variation on the delivery of instruction with a medium-sized effect. Osuji (2016) investigated impact of organizational facilities on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Giwa and Zaria Education Zones, Kaduna State, Nigeria. Findings of the study among others revealed that there is no significant difference in the opinions of employees and employers on the impact of teaching facilities on students' job productivity in Public Secondary Organizationals in Giwa and Zaria Education Zones in Kaduna State. Also, finding shows that there is no significant difference in the view of respondents on the impact of welfare/health facilities on students' job productivity s in secondary organizationals in Giwa and Zaria Education Zones in Kaduna State. In view of the findings, it was concluded that organizational facilities remain one essential factor in the realization of the goals of secondary education.

Methodology

The study adopted the correlational research design. The area of the study is Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma, Edo State. The institution is located along express Way, KM 70 Benin Auchu Rd, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. The population of the study was made up of all the 1,432 non-academic staff in all the units which the non-teaching staff function in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. The purposive sampling technique was adopted in selecting 8 units/department of the non-teaching staff while the simple random sampling technique was adopted in selecting a sample size of 300 non-academic staff from units/department in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. These included Verification unit, Audit, Bursary, Post-Graduate Studies, Admission Unit, Information Communication Technology (ICT) Unit, Exams and Records and Senate Services Unit. Both primary and secondary data were the main sources of data used in this study. Concerning the field data method, the study used a questionnaire to elicit responses from the respondents. The researcher collected secondary information from different sources like; textbooks, internet, newspaper, magazines and journals. This information was reviewed by visiting places such as libraries and internet cafes and this type of information was used supplement the collected data from different categories of the respondents. The study used panel secondary data to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses. The secondary data were obtained using questionnaire. An adapted questionnaire titled Organizational Climate and Employees Productivity Questionnaire (OCEPQ) was used to elicit responses from the respondents. The method which was adopted in the analysis of data for this study was percentage and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) statistical tool. The hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between job autonomy and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Coefficient analysis of the relationship between job autonomy and employees productivity of non-academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State

Variable	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	r-cal	P-Value	Remark
Job Autonomy	300	3.60	.548	298	.667	.009	H₀ hypothesis rejected (p<.05)
Employees Productivity		2.80	.954				

The data in Table 1: showed the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient analysis of the relationship between job autonomy and productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. The Pearson r of .667 was found to be significant at a P-value of .009 ($.009 \leq .05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between job autonomy and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State was rejected. This result indicated that there is a significant relationship between job autonomy and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between job involvement and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Coefficient analysis of the relationship between job involvement and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State

Variable	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	r-cal	P-Value	Remark
Job Involvement	300	2.80	.837	298	.500	.0001	H₀ hypothesis rejected (p<.05)
Employees Productivity		3.50	.452				

The data in table1: showed the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient analysis of the relationship between job involvement and employees productivity in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. The Pearson r of .500 was found to be significant at a P-value of .0001 ($.0001 \leq .05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between job involvement and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State was rejected. This result indicated that there is a significant relationship between job involvement and productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between concern for employee welfare and employees productivity in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Coefficient analysis of the relationship between concern for employee welfare and productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State

Variable	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	r-cal	P-Value	Remark
Concern for Employee Welfare	300	2.40	.401	298	.721	.0011	H₀ hypothesis rejected (p<.05)
Employees Productivity		1.80	.447				

The data in Table 3 showed the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient analysis of the relationship between concern for employee welfare and employees productivity in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. The Pearson r of .721 was found to be significant at a P-value of .0011 ($.0011 \leq .05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis

which states that there is no significant relationship between concern for employee welfare and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State was rejected. This result indicated that there is a significant relationship between concern for employee welfare and employees productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant relationship between organizational facilities and employees' productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli university, Ekpoma, Edo State

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Coefficient analysis of the relationship between organizational facilities and employees' productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli university, Ekpoma, Edo State

Variable	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	r-cal	P-Value	Remark
Organizational facilities	300	1.80	.954	298	.394	.004	H₀ hypothesis rejected (p<.05)
Training of Teachers		3.80	.447				
Employees Productivity							

The data in Table 4 showed the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient analysis of the relationship between organizational facilities and productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli university, Ekpoma, Edo State. The Pearson r of .394 was found to be significant at a P-value of .004 ($.004 \leq .05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between organizational facilities and employees' productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli university, Ekpoma, Edo State was rejected. This result indicated that there is a significant relationship between organizational facilities and productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli university, Ekpoma, Edo State.

Discussion of Findings

Job Autonomy and Employees Productivity

The finding of hypothesis one revealed that there is a significant relationship between job autonomy and productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State Nigeria. The finding of this study is in agreement with that of Bakker (2004) that job resources which includes autonomy, supervisory coaching, social support and performance feedback have positively influenced the balance between teachers' skills and challenges, which in turn contributes to their work enjoyment and intrinsic work motivation. This finding is also in agreement with that of Mworiali, Wachira and Mwaura (2021) that there was a significant relationship between job autonomy and employee performance and that job autonomy influences employee performance in county government of Isiolo. Contrarily, this finding is not in agreement with that Saragih (2011) that there was no significant relationship between job autonomy and job performance but this research showed that job satisfaction significantly related to job performance.

Job Involvement and Employees Productivity

The finding of hypothesis two revealed that there is a significant relationship between job involvement and productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. The finding of this study is in line with that of Kusmaningtyas and Nugroho (2020) what should that Involvement has a significant influence on Work Engagement, but Job Involvement has no significant influence on Employee Performance, while Work Engagement has a significant influence on Employee Performance. The finding of this study is also in line with that of Mazayed, Khan, Kundi, Qureshi, Akhtar Bila (2014) that a significant positive relationship exist between job involvements, employee's commitment and organizational productivity and that organizations with high job involvement and employees' commitment are performing well than organizations with little job involvement and low employees' commitment.

Concern for Employee Welfare and Employees Productivity

The finding of this study showed that there is a significant relationship between concern for employee welfare and productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. The finding of this study is in line with that of Aldaibat, and Irtaimeh, (2012) that training benefits that encompass both personal benefit and career benefit correlate significantly to organizational commitment components of, affective, instrumental and normative and that involvement in training assist employees interact, improve their productivity, personal growth as well as develop career wise, opening new opportunities of for new careers. The finding of this study is also in agreement with that of Agusioma, Nyakwara and Mwiti (2019) whose study found that staff welfare was positively and significantly affected employee performance and that an increase in these factors will result in increased accessibility to increased employee performance. The study concludes that staff welfare is essential in creating a sense of recognition and satisfaction among the employees which improves their productivity.

Organizational Facilities and Employee Productivity

The finding of this study indicated that there is a significant relationship between organizational facilities and productivity of non academic staff in Ambrose Alli university, Ekpoma, Edo State. The finding of this study supports that of Kiptum (2018) that the physical facilities, classroom arrangement and work environment had significant relationship with employees' satisfaction. The finding of this study is in line with that of Ibrahim (2009) that six of the ten facility conditions are statically and positively associated with the delivery of instruction. These six facility conditions significantly predicted the delivery of instruction after controlling other extraneous or plausible variables. Facility conditions accounted for 43 percent of the explained variation on the delivery of instruction with a medium-sized effect. The finding of this study also supports that of Osuji (2016) that there is no significant difference in the opinions of employees and employers on the impact of teaching facilities on teacher job productivity in Public Secondary Organizationals in Giwa and Zaria Education Zones in Kaduna State.

Conclusions

From the above analysis, we have reached the conclusion that organizational climate is useful in increasing employees, productivity. Factors like job autonomy, job involvement, concern for employee welfare and organizational facilities are useful in creating an organizational climate that has positive impact on employees level of productivity. The results send a useful information to organizations particularly tertiary academic institutions that by developing a conducive organizational climate, the level of productivity of employees particularly non-teaching staff can be increased and sustained

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. The university management should ensure that employees are given a reasonable and commendable job autonomy in their various unit as this would enhance their level of job productivity.
2. The employees should consider direct involvement of employees in the process of decision making as this would help them improve on their job productivity.
3. The university management should be directly involved in the provision of welfare packages to employees as this could help in the enhancement of their job productivity.
4. The state government should be effective in the provision of modern and usable facilities for the discharge of their duties which could enhance their job productivity

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